

Custom interfaces for curating metadata in the GLAM domain

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1 Object of study

Curating metadata about galleries, libraries, archives, and museums (GLAM) is a task that can only be completed successfully if professional human users are involved in the curation process. On the one hand, museologists, archivists and librarians have interpretative skills in their respective domains that cannot be replicated by software. On the other hand, using algorithms to generate, modify, disseminate and preserve cultural heritage data is often the very cause of the introduction of “errors/horrors” [1].

However, the advent of digital has made the curators’ task more difficult and time-consuming, requiring them to supplement their sectoral knowledge with technical notions. The representation of data in machine-readable formats (CSV, XML, JSON, RDF) and their preservation in heterogeneous databases (relational, non-relational and graphs) have introduced a barrier between the data and the domain expert without computer knowledge.

The learning curve became hyperbolic with the introduction of Semantic Web technologies, whose potential is equal to their complexity. They have found widespread use in the humanities, adding semantics to raw data, enabling machines to infer new knowledge and humans to perform searches unthinkable with previous tools. Different disciplines - not to mention individual projects - have devised different ontologies and vocabularies, forming an intricate archipelago with hundreds of standards [2]. Paradoxically, this technological progress, on the one hand, has made human intervention critical - because it is impossible to automate the semantic interpretation of data - and on the other hand, has restricted the number of curators to Semantic Web experts.

The shortage of technical curators had two consequences: collections containing semantic data needed more staff to maintain them. Conversely, traditional datasets did not adopt Semantic Web technologies to avoid curatorial problems. The FICLIT Digital Library and OpenCitations - two projects within the Department of Classical Philology and Italianistics of the University of Bologna (FICLIT) - represent both sides.

The FICLIT Digital Library is the digital version of the archives and cultural collections held and maintained by FICLIT. The data and metadata within it are managed via Omeka S, a content management system designed explicitly for digital exhibitions. Its semantic tools are limited to forcing the use of a standard vocabulary for metadata, which by default is Dublin Core [3]. Nonetheless, the information is organised in a relational database, and SPARQL queries are impossible. Finally, there is no change tracking system or transparent provenance management: the agents responsible for the data are only known in the backend. At the same time, unknown are the source of information, the date on which it was recorded or any previous discordant information.

In contrast, OpenCitations natively uses Semantic Web technologies to publish open bibliographic and citation data [4]. The source of this data is Crossref [5], which obtains it from publishers but does not check it. In the current situation, millions of citations are lost due to invalid DOIs and an equally large number of bibliographic metadata is affected by severe errors [6]. Some can be

corrected automatically based on patterns; others are context-dependent and evident only to the human eye but unmanageable by software.

As a solution to this problem, this project proposes developing a framework for generating interfaces that allow non-technical domain experts to easily enrich and edit metadata in a semantic manner that is agnostic to the underlying ontology model and formats. This objective brings numerous problems related to provenance, customisation and interfacing with the data.

The provenance of a resource is defined as the record describing the persons, institutions, entities and activities involved in the production or distribution of that resource [7]. In other words, who modified the data, how, when, and what the source of the information was. Indeed, the integrity of a statement can only be verified with such documentation and a system to explore it. Moreover, in many humanities disciplines, the very concept of truth loses its meaning without provenance since truth is defined as a statement for which there are trustworthy supporting sources, direct or indirect. As if this were not enough, sources may be at odds with each other, and it is crucial to keep track of such conjectures [8].

Furthermore, the interface must be customisable, as different domains use different conceptual models to represent different kinds of resources (a painting, a record, a document). Therefore, it is unfeasible to develop a universal high-level interface.

There are multiple metadata models, and data can be exposed in heterogeneous ways. It is possible to encounter RDF serialisations (e.g. JSON-LD), triplestore (e.g. Blazegraph), tabular formats (e.g. CSV), relational databases (e.g. MySQL), hierarchical formats (e.g. JSON, XML), non-relational databases (e.g. MongoDB, eXist-db). For this reason, a mapping meta-language must be found that allows interfacing with different data formats or databases.

From these considerations, the following research questions emerge:

- How can non-technical GLAM experts be allowed to curate metadata without knowing either the format or the data model?
- How can customisable metadata editors be generated from heterogeneous data models?
- How to interface with heterogeneous data formats, both read and write?

2 Related works

2.1 Metadata in the GLAM domain

The landscape of metadata models for cultural heritage is vast and heterogeneous because there are different objects to be described and different reference institutions.

At the international level, the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA) and the Library of Congress (LOC) deal with

standards for libraries [9, 10], the International Council on Archives (ICA) for archives [11] and the International Council of Museums (ICOM) for museums [12].

The IFLA Library Reference Model represents the sum of all previous standards for describing a bibliographic resource (ISBD and FRBR) and its related authorities (FRAD and FRSAD). One of its stated goals is to provide a conceptual model on which to base ontologies for LOD applications [13]. In fact, the FaBiO ontology [14] is based on the Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records (FRBR) - integrated with the IFLA-RM.

Mirroring the IFLA-LRM, the Records in Contexts - Conceptual Model (RIC-CM) subsumed all previous standards for finding aids (ISAD(G)), as well as for the description of entities, persons and families related to the records contained in an archive (ISAAR(CPF)) [15]. Finally, the Encoded Archival Context - Corporate Bodies, Persons, and Families (EAC-CPF) ontology is based on RIC-CM [16].

2.2 Ontologies for wiki

The overview of metadata in the GLAM domain shows how mature the results are in ontology design. Unfortunately, there are not many examples of software that exploit such metadata models to generate customised interfaces. In the past, the problem has been addressed through “ontologies for wikis”, i.e. wiki-style editors dynamically produced from an ontology so that the data entered was valid concerning the conceptual model, classifiable and searchable in a sophisticated manner..

The first wiki based on an ontology was IkeWiki [17] (evolved into KiwiWiki [18]): once an OWL ontology is loaded, the system automatically converts it into a set of wiki pages and semantic links, editable through a WYSIWYG editor with autocomplete and SPARQL support. A similar approach was adopted by SweetWiki [19], emphasising folksonomies, and by Gaffe [20] and CLEF [21], with more emphasis on customisation. None of these proposals offers a change tracking system with the related provenance metadata. Moreover, in all three cases, the only format considered is RDF.

2.3 Meta-languages

In order to realise an interface agnostic to the underlying metadata formats, it is essential to think about a meta-language that performs the task of a lingua franca. As we have seen, the ontologies and metadata models used in the GLAM domain have all gone toward a language based on triples. It is reasonable to imagine that the lingua franca should also be based on triples.

A long history of mapping languages for transforming heterogeneous sources into RDF can be considered outperformed by RML [22]. It is based on a series of declarative mappings, which allow the incorporation of specific queries for different formats, such as SQL and XPath. The main limitation of RML is its syntax, which is designed to be easily readable by a machine but not by a

human being. To overcome this obstacle, a graphical editor, RMLEditor [23], and an easier-to-read textual solution based on YAML, YARRRML [24] have been proposed. The ecosystem of software revolving around RML is vast: for instance, there is a web interface for producing valid YARRRML called Matey [24], software in JAVA that generates RDF from a source and RML/YARRRML file [25], or from a data stream [26], to name a few.

3 Research objectives

At the end of the project, the following results will be produced:

- A framework for generating interfaces that allow domain experts but non-technical human users to curate metadata related to the GLAM domain. Special attention will be given to change tracking, provenance, customisation and interfacing with heterogeneous formats.
- Two distinct implementations for two use cases, namely, an interface for curating the FICLIT Digital Library and one for OpenCitations. As the two collections use different technologies, two plugins will be realised to allow the framework to interact respectively with Omeka S for the FICLIT DL and with a triplestore (e.g., Blazegraph) for OpenCitations.
- Rich documentation to ensure software reuse.
- One or more articles describing the results obtained.

The source code will be distributed under an open source licence [27] and with special attention to FAIR principles [28].

Therefore, the software will be:

- *Findable e Accessible* — the software will be available on GitHub, and each version will be assigned a DOI via Zenodo. Its long-term preservation will be entrusted to Software Heritage [29].
- *Interoperable e Reusable* — the software will be written in a widely used language (e.g. Python), and its dependencies will be documented to facilitate reuse in heterogeneous development environments. Furthermore, all dependencies will be open source, so the licence adopted can be as open as possible (e.g. ISC).

The following paragraphs describe how the issues introduced in the previous sections will be addressed, leaving the possibility of modifying the approach later in development. Figure 1 provides an overview of the architecture of the proposed framework.

To address the problem of software genericity concerning heterogeneous models, the “Model-View-Controller” (MVC) design pattern will be adopted [30]. The “model” represents the data structure; the “view” is what is shown to the

Figure 1: Framework architecture

end user, while the “controller” is the component that manages the interaction between the user and the application. According to the MVC model, the three components are independent of each other, and it is possible to change one at any time without affecting the functioning of the application. In this case, the “model” is the format in which the metadata and its conceptual organisation are exposed. The “controller” handles the transformation of data into triples, the generation of the graphical interface, and the tracking of changes and their provenance. Finally, the “view” is the metadata editor with which the curator interacts.

In order to implement the framework, existing solutions and software will be reused wherever possible. In particular, the CLEF [21] software will be considered a starting point for generating wiki-style editors from a metadata model.

Regarding the tracking of changes and their provenance, the author of this project has already addressed this issue by developing the Python library, time-agnostic-library [31]. It allows data to be explored in its latest version and throughout its history, providing information on who made what change, when and the source used [32].

Finally, RML [22] is an excellent starting point for interfacing with different data formats, as it has a rich ecosystem of well-documented software and is currently up-to-date. However, RML will need to be extended to allow the conversion of different formats into RDF and their modification. Facade-X [33] is also a valid reference model because it is compatible with SPARQL, although, like RML, it only allows reading and not writing data to date.

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